

Split Delivery Application in Vehicle Routing Problem with Drones

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Abstract

The use of drones for last-mile parcel delivery has attracted popularity of attention, especially among online retailers and food delivery platforms that pursuit a fast and high-quality one-to-one service. However, previous works disregarded or assumed the load capacity of drones as fixed values for simplification in truck-drone delivery, such that there is no split delivery assignments on drones. Yet in real-world applications, considering drone endurance and payload capacity, it is highly practical that they deliver in a split way. This paper concerns the novel variant: the split delivery vehicle routing problem with drones (VRPD-S). We deal with the cases where each truck is equipped with a single drone, for serving a set of customers with minimal delivery duration. This problem is challenging since drones can perform multiple deliveries for a single customer node, i.e., the customers' demands are allowed to be split. Whereas trucks follow the vehicle routing problem and meanwhile need to synchronize with drones at the depot or demand points. We model this problem as a mixed-integer linear program and implement a problem-guided predictive search combined with an adaptive large neighborhood search (PS-ALNS) procedure to solve it. Extensive computational experiments were carried out on benchmark instances available in the literature. According to the numerical results, our model is validated and the proposed algorithm works effectively in small and larger instances. Split deliveries can generate savings both in terms of number of vehicles and travel costs, and lead to more flexible and efficient results for the overall delivery system.

Key words: Split delivery, Truck-drone system, Vehicle routing problem with drones, Last-mile delivery, Integer programming, Metaheuristics

1. Introduction

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have several uses in civic and industrial settings, including transportation, telecommunication, and agriculture [Macrina et al. \(2020\)](#). Numerous sensors are included in drones, and these capabilities allow for automatic flight, object tracking, and collision avoidance. Drones are light in weight and flexible in route shifting. And owing to the more advanced battery with high energy density, the rapid development of drone delivery is a heated topic in last-mile delivery. There is also a growing body of research on drone-related routing problems in academia in recent years.

However, utilizing drones along for delivery has possible limitations. The known limits of operational delivery drones include flying range, constrained payload, infrastructure that is densely inhabited, stringent urban airspace regulations, and weather conditions. It is crucial to consider the characteristics of drones and examine the operating variables in the overall operation process. Otherwise, a decision may result in overestimating or underestimating capital requirements.

Therefore, instead of delivery solely by drones, truck-drone delivery emerges to leverage their complementary advantages and compensate for the shortages, as one of the promising drone applications to deliver parcels collaboratively with trucks. On one hand, the advent of the drone to aid truck delivery requires less capital investment than package delivery solely served by truck [Choi & Schonfeld \(2017\)](#). On the other hand, drones along for delivery have certain drawbacks in low energy capacity, comparatively small load capacity, and high maintenance cost. Mutual complementarity within such a delivery system enables improved coping with traffic congestion, environmental conditions, and human intervention, and mitigating environmental impact intensity.

However, in previous works for simplification in truck-drone delivery modeling, the load capacity of drones is disregarded or assumed to be fixed values, such that limited studies focus on the split delivery assignments on drones. Yet in real-world applications, drone capacities are much smaller than that of the truck, thus many customer nodes with large demand cannot be carried by a single drone only once. For customer nodes with large demands, previous works imposed the limitation for them to be only served by truck [Luo et al. \(2021\)](#), which leads to inflexible and inefficient results for the overall delivery system. Considering drone endurance and payload

1 capacity, it is highly practical that they deliver in a split way. Therefore, multiple flights for goods
2 delivery should be considered, which is known as split delivery. More specifically, customers are
3 allowed to be visited more than once. The subject of split delivery should be drones, thanks to their
4 flexible scheduling and transportation, thus more realistic for practical application. Split deliveries
5 can generate savings both in terms of the number of vehicles and travel costs. Therefore, we
6 propose the novel incorporation of drones in the split delivery vehicle routing problem (VRPD-S).

7 Previous works on split delivery are limited to certain transportation scenarios such as truck and
8 ship [Gulczynski et al. \(2010\)](#). In [Toth & Vigo \(2002\)](#), the well-known capacitated vehicle routing
9 problem (CVRP) is proposed, in which a fixed fleet of delivery vehicles of uniform capacity must
10 service known customer demands for a single commodity from a common depot at minimum transit
11 cost. The split delivery vehicle routing problem is a relaxation of CVRP, where the customers'
12 demands are allowed to be split ([Archetti & Speranza \(2008\)](#)). However, only trucks are involved
13 in the modeling. In this work, drones are utilized for split delivery whereas the fleet follows the
14 settings in VRP and returns to the starting point at the end of dispatch. In this way, the economic
15 cost of the split delivery process can be reduced, and the scheduling of drones is more flexible
16 compared to trucks.

17 Challenges within the drone integrated split delivery need to be resolved with more studies.
18 Both the classic traveling salesman problem (TSP) and the vehicle routing problem (VRP) denote
19 the vehicles to traverse all nodes with no repeated visit, despite whether a single vehicle or a fleet
20 is considered. Thus the integration of drone routing management, visiting each demand point
21 only once, into such an application framework is more straightforward than VRPD-S. Because
22 the split delivery problem with drones is comprised of the modeling difficulty and the NP-hard
23 nature in multiple visits to one node within a graph, let alone the application scenario in truck-drone
24 coordination system that requires an even higher degree of drone and truck cooperation [Zhou et al.](#)

25 Concerning the algorithms to solve split delivery problem with vehicles, exact solution methods
26 and heuristic methods are mainly contained. Using new classes of valid inequalities that were
27 included into a cutting-plane method, a mixed integer programming (MIP) formulation for the
28 split delivery truck routing issue with infinite fleet is described in [Archetti et al. \(2011a\)](#). Heuristic
29 algorithms are more promising for practical application because the majority of accurate approaches

1 are useful for small-scale situations. In [Paul et al. \(2021\)](#), a three-phase Tabu Search (TS) heuristic is
2 proposed for the split delivery vehicle routing problem with unlimited fleet. Furthermore, heuristics
3 algorithms in this field is limited, let alone the algorithms developed to solve split delivery problem
4 with certain scale of customer number. Thus, more works are required to be implemented in this
5 field. More importantly, to the best of our knowledge, there has not been algorithms developed
6 to tackle the split delivery vehicle routing problem with drones. In this paper, we propose an
7 efficient approach utilizing predictive search combined with an adaptive large neighborhood search
8 (PS-ALNS) algorithm to solve the drone integrated split delivery problem.

9 To address the above issues, in this paper we propose for the first time the novel variant of
10 VRPD, in the drone split delivery application scenario, and the PS-ALNS algorithm is developed
11 duly. The objective of the split delivery vehicle routing problem with drones (VRPD-S) is to
12 minimize the latest time (i.e. makespan) of all trucks and drones, under the constraint that all
13 customers' demands are either delivered entirely by a single vehicle or split among drones. The
14 proposed model formulation considers not only the basics of the truck-drone delivery scenario,
15 but also the split delivery representation. For the synchronization of truck and drone, the widely
16 used way of drone launch and retrieval on customer nodes is adopted. The performance of the
17 proposed heuristic algorithm is verified on newly generated instances extended from [Belenguer
18 et al. \(2000\)](#). The established PS-ALNS approach outperforms solver results for medium-scale
19 examples, whereas small-scale instances may be solved directly using commercial solvers. The
20 main contributions of this paper are:

- 21 1. Introduce a new VRPD variation that takes drone split delivery into account. Additionally,
22 practical restrictions like the modeling of drones' durability are taken into account.
- 23 2. Create a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) model for the problem that takes into
24 account the synchronization of truck-drone pairs, the drone split delivery scenario and the
25 truck-drone delivery system. From the formulation, managerial insights and distinctive
26 aspects of the problem may be deduced.
- 27 3. Propose a problem-guided predictive search combined with an adaptive large neighbor-
28 hood search (PS-ALNS) heuristic algorithm that integrates machine learning and heuristic

1 search into a single framework. The algorithm is designed to solve larger-scale instances
2 efficiently. Duly apply numerical tests based on generated benchmark instances to evaluate
3 the performance of the proposed algorithm.

4 **2. Related Works**

5 This review focuses on comprehensive literature regarding drone and truck collaboration in
6 delivery service, the split delivery operation mechanism, and relevant modeling techniques and
7 solution algorithms.

8 *2.1. Drone-aided Delivery Problem*

9 This section reviews relevant literature where trucks and drones are deployed together for last-
10 mile delivery, which deploys one or multiple vehicles with drones to serve the customers and allows
11 the drone to visit one or multiple customers during a single flight. Since the introduction of the
12 truck-drone delivery system in [Murray & Chu \(2015\)](#), related studies have increased rapidly. Drone-
13 aided routing problems originate from traveling salesman problem (TSP) and have demonstrated a
14 great advantage with the drone-aided per truck over the truck-only delivery. In the majority of the
15 studies, drone delivery has been viewed as a partially automated service, with vehicles handling
16 line-haul and heavyweight deliveries ([Agatz et al., 2018](#); [Poikonen et al., 2019](#)). Delivery supported
17 by trucks reduces delivery time compared to a truck-only system. Besides, package delivery by
18 drones requires less capital investment than delivery solely by truck [Macrina et al. \(2020\)](#). The
19 consideration of environmental impact is a crucial aspect as well, where drones can deliver parcels
20 to nearby recipients while trucks deliver to more remote customers.

21 Variants of the drone-related routing problem associated with various exact algorithms have
22 been developed for truck-drone delivery allocation. The primary distinction between the traveling
23 salesman problem with drones (TSP-D) and the flying sidekick traveling salesman problem (FSTSP)
24 is that the TSP-D model forbids drone excursions that start and terminate at the depot directly
25 ([Bouman et al., 2018](#); [Yurek & Ozmutlu, 2018](#); [Ha et al., 2018, 2020](#)). In [Poikonen et al. \(2019\)](#) a
26 branch-and-bound approach for the TSP-D is designed, which can solve instances with 20 nodes
27 to optimality. In [Cavani et al. \(2021\)](#) the traveling salesman problem with multiple drones is

1 considered. A branch-and-cut algorithm is proposed, which can solve instances with 25 customers
2 and 3 drones to optimality. A two-stage mixed-integer programming model for the TSP-D is created
3 in [Vásquez et al. \(2021\)](#). They plan the truck route to visit a subset of clients in the initial phase.
4 The drone plan is optimized in the second step using the outputs from the first stage's problem
5 as inputs. A decomposition algorithm of the Benders type is created based on the structure of
6 their model. In [Roberti & Ruthmair \(2021\)](#) a compact formulation for the TSP-D is constructed
7 and a branch-and-price algorithm is developed, which can solve instances up to 39 customers to
8 optimality.

9 Concerning cooperative deliveries by drone and truck associated with heuristics solution meth-
10 ods, in [Agatz et al. \(2018\)](#), it is suggested to use a truck-first-drone-second heuristic and a more
11 effective dynamic programming-based approach to solve the traveling salesman problem with
12 drones (TSP-D). In [Wang et al. \(2017\)](#), the vehicle routing problem with flexible drones (VRP-D) is
13 created as a significant expansion of the TSP-D with many vehicles providing simultaneous services.
14 By examining how the number of drones per truck and the drones' speed might effect the greatest
15 savings from employing drones, the worst-case assessments are offered. According to [Schermer
16 et al. \(2018\)](#), a mixed integer linear program is put forth with a two-stage heuristic to build the
17 initial solution in the first step and local search to enhance it in the second. Using a combination of
18 the drone's battery life, cost metrics, and the fixed cost of deploying drones, [Poikonen et al. \(2017\)](#)
19 explored the same issue by determining upper boundaries on the amount of time saved by drone
20 operations.

21 However, difficulties and fundamental issues also exist for hybrid delivery services. The
22 cooperative truck-drone routing issues are best understood as a synthesis of the following sub-
23 problems: a drone routing issue with payload capacity and flight endurance constraints, a TSP
24 issue with precedence constraints, and a synchronization issue between the truck schedules and
25 drone landings. There are a wide range of strategies for synchronization within the coordinated
26 routing problems. In this paper, for the simplicity of modeling framework, the widely used tactic of
27 drone launch and retrieval on customer nodes is adopted. Trucks are not allowed to wait at the same
28 location to retrieve the drone after operations, and the drone can only be retrieved by its paired
29 truck.

1 Furthermore, as summarized in [Macrina et al. \(2020\)](#), most of the works consider a single
2 customer visit per drone trip. TSP-D and VRP-D impose a drone's maximum range or flying
3 duration endurance while supposing that the amount of time required to recharge or replace the
4 battery is constant. Though the majority of the papers enforce truck capacity, only some works
5 consider drone capacity. A more advanced model for a drone flight endurance that takes the drone's
6 battery capacity and energy usage into account is currently being suggested to expand FSTSP.
7 Research on drone-aided delivery problems lays the foundation for drone involvement in the split
8 delivery problem.

9 *2.2. Split Delivery System*

10 This section reviews relevant literature with respect to split delivery investigation, where trucks
11 and ships are mainly devised as the subject. The split delivery vehicle routing problem (SDVRP) was
12 first introduced by [Chen et al. \(2007\)](#); [Archetti & Speranza \(2012\)](#), where the authors demonstrated
13 empirically that split deliveries have the advantages to generate savings both in terms of number of
14 vehicles and travel costs. This claim was verified through computational experiments involving
15 a set of 540 instances with up to 150 customers. Generally speaking, SDVRP can be defined
16 with the objective to minimize the sum of the travel costs. The following constraints apply to all
17 routes: every route begins and finishes at the depot; demand can be less than, equal to, or more than
18 capacity; and demand can be provided wholly by one vehicle or distributed among many vehicles,
19 thus consumers may be visited more than once.

20 Variants of the SDVRP associated with various exact approaches have been developed for
21 truck-drone delivery allocation. A mixed integer programming formulation for the SDVRP with
22 infinite fleet (SDVRP-UF) is described in [Archetti et al. \(2011b\)](#), along with new classes of valid
23 inequalities that were included into a cutting-plane method. A polyhedral study on the SDVRP with
24 limited fleet (SDVRP-LF) is carried out in [Archetti et al. \(2011a\)](#), and as a consequence, various
25 classes of legitimate inequalities were constructed and a cutting-plane based method was put into
26 practice. A two-phase precise algorithm for the SDVRP-LF is proposed in [Irnich et al. \(2014\)](#), and
27 a column generation technique is constructed in [Silva et al. \(2015\)](#) for the same variation. A cut-
28 and-price strategy is proposed in [Moreno et al. \(2010\)](#) over an expanded formulation together with

1 new valid inequalities for the SDVRP-LF. A branch-cut-and-price algorithm is recently developed
2 for the SDVRP-LF and SDVRP-UF in [Marques et al. \(2020\)](#). Solution feasibility is ensured in
3 the solution form design of accurate algorithms. However, exact solution techniques have certain
4 limitations in that they can only be used for the SDVRP to solve instances with up to 30 customers
5 in a methodical manner. When compared to the capacitated vehicle routing problem (CVRP), which
6 has precise algorithms that can systematically solve situations with up to 135 clients, this number is
7 limited [Silva et al. \(2015\)](#). Heuristic algorithms, however, appear to be more suitable for dealing
8 with medium-large SDVRP instances.

9 Concerning SDVRP associated with heuristics solution methods, in [Tuzun & Burke \(1999\)](#) a
10 three-phase tabu search (TS) heuristic is proposed for the SDVRP-UF. A hybrid algorithm for the
11 SDVRP-UF is created in [Liu et al. \(2021\)](#) by fusing a savings-based heuristic with a mixed integer
12 programming formulation and a record-to-record process. A scatter search-based approach for the
13 SDVRP-LF is proposed in [Campos et al. \(2001\)](#) with two distinct processes for creating starting
14 populations. A memetic algorithm with population management is created for the SDVRP-UF
15 and three novel neighborhood structures specifically for the SDVRP in [Boudia et al. \(2006\)](#). A
16 hybrid technique is proposed in [Archetti & Speranza \(2014\)](#) that combines a TS heuristic with an
17 integer programming formulation. Constructive and local search techniques for the SDVRP-LF
18 are provided in [Aleman et al. \(2010\)](#), while [Ozsoydan & Sipahioglu \(2013\)](#) implements a TS
19 heuristic with vocabulary building for the SDVRP-UF. A research comparing the performance of
20 several local search-based metaheuristics for the SDVRP-UF is reported in [Derigs et al. \(2010\)](#). A
21 two-phase constructive technique is established for the SDVRP-LF more recently in [Wilck IV &
22 Cavalier \(2012\)](#). A genetic method was also suggested for the same variation.

23 As research on optimization approaches for drones in civil applications has grown rapidly
24 over the last few years. This motivates the potential for drone integrated split delivery, and due
25 to the limited studies, this area should be investigated. Split delivery of truck-drone involves
26 individual drone movements supported by trucks on the basis of single visit per flight. Similar as
27 VRPD settings, drones can be carried by trucks from one dispatching location to another. In the
28 drone integrated split delivery problem, the truck and drone work together to deliver parcels in a
29 combination route. Launching and retrieving drones are crucial in the synchronization of drone and

1 truck routes. It is beneficial to design automatic systems that can handle multiple launching and
2 retrieval of drones simultaneously, which increases the efficiency of last-mile deliveries, and reduce
3 manpower requirement. It is imposed in this paper that trucks are allowed to move to new customer
4 locations to retrieve dispatched drones.

5 2.3. Summary

6 In this paper, we include the following settings for the truck-drone split delivery problem,
7 which not only considers the traits of truck-drone delivery scenario, but also the split delivery
8 representation. We adopt single drone per truck, and single visit per drone flight, and allow each
9 drone to perform multiple back-and-forth trips as split delivery. Without loss of generality and
10 to avoid trivial difficulties, the trucks have identical parameters as a homogeneous fleet. More
11 specifically, the number of drones carried by each truck is identical and the characteristics of each
12 truck/drone are the same. Within the overall graph, a single depot is located, meaning that there
13 is no need to pickup from different depots. The proposed VRPD-S is more practical than earlier
14 research since it makes use of a drone flight endurance model based on battery capacity, power
15 consumption rate, payload of packages, and flight time. Besides, the proposed problem allows
16 multiple drone deliveries at customer nodes.

17 3. Problem Statement and Mathematical Model

18 This section provides a formal description and a MILP formulation of the VRPD-S problem.

19 3.1. Notations and Problem Definition

20 A summary of parameter notations used is presented in Table 1. Superscript "G" and "U" are
21 used to denote the truck and drones, respectively, for more clarity. "G" stands for truck, while
22 "UAV" is a drone. For the simplicity to distinguish notations, customer nodes are classified into the
23 truck node and drone node, which refer to nodes served by truck and drone, respectively.

24 The VRPD-S is defined on a complete and directed graph $G = (V, E)$, where $V = \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$
25 is the vertex set and $E = \{(i, j) : i, j \in V, i \neq j\}$ is the edge set. The single depot is denoted by vertex
26 0. The set of other vertices $C = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is the set of n customers. Each customer is associated

1 with a demand of weight w_i . To satisfy this demand, each customer should be served by either one
2 truck exactly once or by one or more drones one or more times. There is a fleet of homogeneous
3 trucks $K = \{1, \dots, |K|\}$. Each truck is equipped with one drone. The drone has a self-weight w^U and
4 a maximum capacity of Q . The requested time for a truck or a drone to serve a customer node i is
5 denoted with s_i^G, s_i^U , respectively.

6 Since the given drone speed and truck speed are different, the traveling time on an arc by truck
7 and drone are different. t_{ij}^U and t_{ij}^G are used to represent the travelling time for drone and truck on
8 arc (i, j) , respectively. For simplification of modeling, we add $|K|$ dummy nodes to represent the
9 returning to depot 0, such that the k -th truck route will start at node 0 and ends at node $n+k$. Energy
10 consumption is a limitation to drone flight and we adopt the energy consumption model in [Zhang
11 et al. \(2021\)](#), in which a fixed energy consumption rate per weight per time α and the full battery
12 capacity θ is given. The total energy consumption over one drone flight will not exceed the full
13 battery capacity θ .

Table 1: Parameter notation

Notation	Description
C	Set of customers
V	Set of all nodes
E	Set of all edges
K	Set of all truck-drone pairs
t_{ij}^U	Time cost when drone flies along arc $(i, j) \in E$
t_{ij}^G	Time cost when truck travels along arc $(i, j) \in E$
Q	The maximum weight capacity of carried packages by a drone
s_i^U	The time required for a drone to serve customer i
s_i^G	The time required for a truck to serve customer i
w_i	The weight of the demand required by customer i
w^U	The self-weight of a drone
θ	The maximum battery capacity of the drone
α	Battery energy consumption rate per weight per time unit
M	A sufficiently large positive number for the Big M method

14 To provide more explicit description for the problem setups, the schematic diagram for a VRPD-
15 S solution example with 10 customers and 2 truck-drone pairs is illustrated in Fig. 1. A solution to
16 the problem contains information on customer assignments to the truck and drones, the sequences

1 of customers visits by both the truck and drones, as well as the launch and retrieval nodes of all
 2 drone trips. The solution can be represented as a directed acyclic graph, where the customers are
 3 represented as nodes, and the precedence orders of visits by the drone or the truck are represented
 4 using directed arcs.

Figure 1: Trajectory allocation representation for VRPD-S solution example

5 The routes for trucks in the fleet, following time sequence, are: $0 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 0$ (truck 1),
 6 $0 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow 7 \rightarrow 0$ (truck 2), represented by solid directed lines respectively. The
 7 drone associated with truck 1 has routes denoted with red dotted lines. After departing from the
 8 depot, drone 1 serves customer node 8 first and then synchronizes with truck 1 at node 1. Thereafter,
 9 drone 1 visits node 10 from node 2 and synchronizes with truck 1 back at the depot. Similarly for
 10 drone 2, it leaves truck 2 at node 3 to deliver packages to node 9 and returns to truck 2 at node 4. At
 11 node 5, it visits node 9 again and synchronizes with truck 2 at node 6. Immediately then, it serves
 12 node 10 and returns back to truck 2 at node 7.

13 Therefore, to summarize the problem setup in this paper, there are multiple vehicles in the
 14 truck fleet, each equipped with a single drone. The maximum distance and capacities of trucks are
 15 assumed as unlimited, whereas capacities of the drones have certain thresholds. For the trucks, their
 16 routing problem is modeled as VRP, and every route starts and ends at the depot. For the drones,
 17 each drone flight only allows a single visit to one customer node. Each time the drone is launched,
 18 the battery is deemed fully charged with negligible other cost or delay, since this can be achieved
 19 by performing a battery replacement.

20 Meanwhile, for the synchronization between truck and drone in terms of routes and timing,

1 each drone can visit a node multiple times and can visit different nodes as well, but it needs to be
2 dispatched from and return to its originally paired truck at a customer node, meaning that drones
3 are not allowed to be swapped between two trucks. Therefore, the truck and drone routes are
4 synchronized at the landing node of drone. If the truck arrives earlier than drone, it waits for the
5 drone, and vice versa. Besides, if the drone launches from the truck, their leaving time from the
6 current node is the same. The features of drone delivery mechanism constitutes the flexible split
7 delivery for customer nodes, since each node can be served multiple times either by the same drone
8 or by different drones, or served only once by a truck.

9 Experiments on drone deliveries show that they are significantly constrained by payload [Luo](#)
10 [et al. \(2021\)](#) and drone flying duration because the majority of drones are fueled by lithium-ion
11 batteries with low energy consumption. As a result, it is essential to explore drone endurance into
12 modeling, which means that operating limitations should take into account the dependence between
13 battery capacity, power consumption pace, load weight, and delivery distance. The intended
14 capacity of the drone and battery limitations set a limit on how far each drone can fly. We adopt
15 the energy consumption function proposed in [Zhang et al. \(2020\)](#); [Liu et al. \(2020\)](#), where the
16 energy decrease follows linear approximation with the drone self-weight, corresponding payload,
17 and flying time duration. More specifically, on a drone path $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$, the consumed energy
18 contains the loaded drone flight time on arc (i, l) , the unloaded drone flight time on arc (l, j) , and
19 the hovering time at j .

20 3.2. Objective and Decision Variables

21 The objective of this problem is to minimize the maximum completion time incurred for trucks
22 and drones to deliver all required parcels and return to the depot (i.e., to minimize makespan). This
23 is achieved by solving for a series of decision variables summarized in [Table 2](#).

24 We discuss the binary decision variables first. Z_{ik}^G indicates whether the customer node i is
25 served by truck k , and if the node is served by a truck, it will be served by only one truck once.
26 Z_i^U indicates whether customer node i is served by the drone. Since split delivery via drones is
27 considered in this problem, the variable to differentiate if the node is served by truck or drone(s) is
28 sufficient for modeling. To represent the routes for trucks and drones, y_{ij}^k and x_{ijl}^k are utilized. y_{ij}^k

Table 2: List of decision variables

Notation	Description
$Z_{ik}^G \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether customer i is served by truck k
$Z_i^U \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether customer i is served by drone
$y_{ij}^k \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether truck k travels along arc $(i, j) \in E$
$x_{ijl}^k \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether drone k travels along $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$
$N_i^A \in \{0, 1\}$	The number of drones on the truck after arriving i
$N_i^L \in \{0, 1\}$	The number of drones on the truck after leaving i
$0 \leq w_{ijl} \leq Q$	The payload of the drone in path $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$
$t_i^{U,A} \geq 0$	The drone's arrival time at node i
$t_i^{G,A} \geq 0$	The truck's arrival time at node i
$t_i^{G,L} \geq 0$	The truck's (drone's) departure time from node i
$\hat{t}_{ijl}^H \geq 0$	The drone's hovering time at node j

1 indicates whether truck k travels along arc (i, j) , solutions of which show the routes arrangement
2 in VRP. x_{ijl}^k indicates whether drone k travels along path $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$. Three nodes can define each
3 drone path under the problem setting, because each flight contains launching from a customer node,
4 serving a customer node, and returning to the merging node with the truck. Then the number of
5 drones on the truck is represented with N_i^A, N_i^L . As each truck is associated with one drone, thus if
6 the drone launches at node i , the number of drones on the truck after arriving i is 1, and the number
7 of drones on the truck after leaving i is 0. It follows the same principle for a truck to retrieve its
8 paired drone at node i .

9 Furthermore, for continuous decision variables, the following are incorporated into this problem.
10 w_{ijl} denotes the payload of the drone in path $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$, the summation of which is equal to the
11 demand of customer point l , indicating split delivery service and the carried weight in each flight is
12 smaller than drone weight capacity. Then four variables are relevant for truck-drone synchronization
13 in terms of time feasibility. $t_i^{U,A}, t_i^{G,A}$ represent the drone's and the truck's arrival time at node i
14 separately. And $t_i^{G,L}$ denotes the truck's departure time from node i , which is also the departure time
15 for the drone if the drone returns to the truck at this node. Thereafter, if the drone arrives earlier
16 than the truck for synchronization, it hovers for time \hat{t}_{ijl}^H to wait for the truck's arrival at node j ,
17 during which energy consumption is incurred. And if the truck arrives early, there will not be the
18 hovering time and the synchronization happens at the truck-drone leaving time.

1 3.3. Mathematical Formulation

2 An MILP model for the VRPD-S is presented as follows. The constraints of the model are
3 categorized into routing constraints for trucks and drones, duration constraints with endurance
4 modeling, and time constraints for truck-drone synchronization.

$$\min \max\{t_{n+1}^{U,A}, \dots, t_{n+|K|}^{U,A}, t_{n+1}^{G,A}, \dots, t_{n+|K|}^{G,A}\} \quad (1)$$

s.t.

Routing constraints:

$$\sum_{k \in K} Z_{ik}^G + Z_i^U = 1; \forall i \in C \quad (2)$$

$$Z_{ik}^G = \sum_{j \in V} y_{ji}^k; \forall i \in C; \forall k \in K \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} y_{ij}^k = \sum_{j \in V} y_{ji}^k \leq 1; \forall i \in C, \forall k \in K \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{i \in C} y_{0,i}^k = 1; \forall k \in K \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i \in C} y_{i,n+k}^k = 1; \forall k \in K \quad (6)$$

$$x_{ijl}^k \leq \min\{Z_{ik}^G, Z_{jk}^G, Z_l^U\}; \forall i, j, l \in V, k \in K \quad (7)$$

$$t_{ik}^{G,A} \leq t_{jk}^{G,A} + M(1 - x_{ijl}^k); \forall i, j, l \in C, k \in K \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{i \in V} \sum_{j \in V} w_{ijl} \geq w_l - M(1 - Z_l^U); \forall l \in C \quad (9)$$

$$w_{ijl} \leq M \sum_{k \in K} x_{ijl}^k; \forall i, j \in V, l \in C \quad (10)$$

Duration constraints:

$$N_0^A = 1 \quad (11)$$

$$N_j^A \leq N_i^L + \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{m \in C} \sum_{l \in C} x_{mjl}^k + M(1 - \sum_{k \in K} y_{ij}^k); \forall (i, j) \in E \quad (12)$$

$$N_i^L \leq N_i^A - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{m \in C} \sum_{l \in C} x_{iml}^k + M(1 - \sum_{k \in K} Z_{ik}^G); \forall i \in V \quad (13)$$

$$(\hat{t}_{ijl}^H + t_{lj}^U)w^U \alpha + t_{il}^U(w^U + w_{ijl})\alpha \leq \theta; \forall i, j \in V, l \in C \quad (14)$$

Time constraints:

$$t_j^{G,A} \geq t_i^{G,L} + t_{ij}^G - M(1 - \sum_{k \in K} y_{ij}^k); \forall (i, j) \in E \quad (15)$$

$$t_i^{G,L} \geq t_i^{G,A} + s_i^G - M(1 - \sum_{k \in K} Z_{ik}^G); \forall i \in V \quad (16)$$

$$t_i^{G,L} \geq t_i^{U,A} - M(1 - Z_i^G); \forall i \in V \quad (17)$$

$$t_j^{U,A} \geq t_i^{G,L} + t_{il}^U + t_{lj}^U - M(1 - \sum_{k \in K} x_{ijl}^k); \forall i, j \in V, l \in C \quad (18)$$

$$\hat{t}_{ijl}^H \geq t_j^{G,A} - t_i^{U,A} + M(1 - \sum_{k \in K} x_{ijl}^k); \forall i, j \in V, l \in C \quad (19)$$

1 The objective function (1) minimizes the total makespan for the truck-drone routes network.
 2 The terms represent the arrival time for the drone and truck returning to the depot denoted by
 3 dummy nodes.

4 In routing constraints, drone trips, truck routes and truck-drone combined routes are included
 5 and confined to comply with the problem settings. Constraint (2) ensures that each customer is
 6 served by either a truck or drone(s). Constraint (3) enforces that if a customer node is visited by a
 7 truck, it should be served by exactly one of the trucks. Flow constraint (4) guarantees the inflow of
 8 truck number equals to the outflow of truck number at customer node i , which is not the depot nor
 9 the end point of truck routes. Then constraints (5)-(6) follow, indicating that there is only outflow
 10 of truck at the depot and inflow of truck at the last served customer (dummy nodes), respectively.
 11 Constraints (7)-(8) together ensure the feasibility of the path $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$ visited by the k -th drone,
 12 such that the drone departs from the paired truck at i and returns at j after traveling through
 13 $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$. In which constraint (7) requires the k -th truck to visit nodes i, j and meanwhile the drone
 14 to serve node l . If the drone travels through $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$, the big M method is utilized in (8) to ensure
 15 the truck arriving time at i is earlier than that at j . Constraints (9)-(10) together guarantee that the
 16 demand assigned to each drone route is viable, which provides the feasibility of split delivery. In
 17 which constraint (9) provides that if the node l is served by drone(s), the sum of payload for drone
 18 path passing l is larger than the weight of package required by customer l . Constraint (10) indicates
 19 that if no drone goes through $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$, the payload allocated to path $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$ should be 0.

20 In duration constraints, the following constraints that represent the schedule of the drone trips
 21 and appropriately model drone flight endurance limitations are outlined. Constraints (11)-(13)
 22 together denote the feasibility of truck-drone routes. Constraint (11) denotes that each truck is
 23 associated with a drone at the depot. Constraint (12) represents that if one truck travels through
 24 arc (i, j) , the number of drones in the truck when it arrives at j equals that when this truck leaves i
 25 plus the number of drones retrieved at j . Constraint (13) expresses that if one truck passes node i ,

1 the number of drones in the truck when it arrives at i equals that when this truck leaves i plus the
2 number of drones launched at i . Constraint (14) ensures that the battery energy consumption does
3 not exceed the battery capacity, which is the endurance constraint. The loaded weight of drones has
4 a significant effect on drone flight time.

5 In time constraints, the feasibility of truck-drone cooperation schedules and synchronization
6 is outlined. Constraint (15) guarantees if the truck travels on arc (i, j) , the truck arriving time at
7 customer j is larger than or equal to the truck leaving time at i plus the truck travel time on arc (i, j) ,
8 which defines the time order for truck routes. And for a customer node i , constraint (16) ensures
9 if the node is served by a truck, the truck leaving time should be its arriving time plus the time
10 requested to serve the node. Then constraint (17) shows if the drone is to be retrieved at node i , the
11 truck has to wait for the drone before its leaving. In constraint (18), if the drone travels through
12 path $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$, the drone arriving time at j is the drone leaving time at i plus the drone flight
13 time on arcs (i, l) and (l, j) . Constraint (19) shows that if the drone travels through $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$, the
14 hovering time for the drone to wait for the paired truck at j is larger than the truck arrival time at j
15 subtracting the drone arrival time.

16 **4. Heuristic Algorithm**

17 In this section, constructive procedures of the proposed heuristics approach are demonstrated.
18 Although the MILP model can be tackled by off-the-shelf solvers like CPLEX and Gurobi for
19 small-size instances, solvers usually cannot provide optimal solutions for medium- or large-size
20 instances in a reasonable computing time, because the VRPD-S problem is NP-hard, and it reduces
21 to the VRP when the set of drones is empty, which is a well-known NP-hard problem. To solve
22 VRPD-S instances more efficiently, this section introduces the PS-ALNS algorithm.

23 More specifically, within the proposed PS-ALNS algorithm, firstly the general overall algorithm
24 framework is introduced in section 4.1. Then, the predictive search method tailored to the problem
25 in this work is discussed in section 4.2, where in each iteration the subproblem of VRPD-S is
26 generated and solved with ALNS. Lastly, the ALNS procedures used to solve the subproblem are
27 discussed in section 4.3.

1 *4.1. General PS-ALNS Framework*

2 The predictive search formulation is first proposed in [Wu \(2022\)](#), where it is utilized to solve
 3 a Capacitated Multi-Item Lot Sizing Problem. An example of PS is demonstrated in their work
 4 to explain its usefulness for solving large-size MILP. More explicitly, the applicability of PS for
 5 large-size MILP is elaborated below. Consider a MILP with the following formulation:

$$\mathcal{P} = \min a \cdot u + b \cdot y \tag{20a}$$

$$\text{Subject to : } c \cdot u + d \cdot y \geq e \tag{20b}$$

$$u \in \mathbb{R}^m \tag{20c}$$

$$y \in [0, 1]^n \tag{20d}$$

6 where u denotes continuous decision variable and y denotes discrete decision variable, and
 7 a, b, c, d, e are coefficients with compatible dimensions. It is noteworthy that when all discrete
 8 variables y are fixed, the above problem is converted into a tractable linear optimization problem.
 9 In [Wu \(2022\)](#), the general predictive search is employed to iteratively decide the values for discrete
 10 variables y . More specifically, a set of indices of binary variables y is maintained, in which the
 11 corresponding values of y are fixed. In each iteration, the set is enlarged by including other indices,
 12 which are decided by an index selection process. After that, a heuristic algorithm is applied to obtain
 13 a feasible solution for the MILP under the case that binary variables in the set are predetermined.

14 This method can help solve the Lot Sizing Problem, however, when the problem is more
 15 complex, as the VRPD-S problem proposed in this paper, this method cannot be applied directly,
 16 with the main difficulties as follows.

- 17 • In the VRPD-S problem, the number of discrete variables is very large. If the predictive search
 18 method is used to search for the optimal solution for all discrete variables, the searching
 19 space is large as well, thus time-consuming in the searching step.
- 20 • The VRPD-S problem has a special structure that certain constraints must be followed under
 21 the value of discrete variables. For example, the values of truck visiting node Z_{ik}^G are required

1 to form a valid route for the truck, otherwise, the solution is invalid. If we simply apply the
 2 predictive search method, it is of the high probability that the solution is infeasible.

3 Therefore, to overcome these difficulties, we adjust the search space of the original predictive
 4 search method. Instead of searching for the values of all discrete variables, we only search for the
 5 value of Z_i^U , which decides the nodes visited by drones. In the corresponding subproblem, where
 6 the nodes visited by drones are determined, the ALNS approach is integrated to find the truck routes
 7 and drone routes under this condition.

8 To better elaborate, the PS-ALNS algorithm, some definitions, and notations are introduced first.
 9 Given a problem of n customers, there are n binary variables $\{Z_1^U, Z_2^U, \dots, Z_n^U\}$ indicating whether
 10 customer i is served by drone or not. The predictive search part decides the value of all Z_i^U . After
 11 that, the ALNS algorithm is leveraged to solve the subproblem with fixed Z_i^U and derive the routes
 12 for each truck and drone. The best-known solution of Z_i^U is denoted as \hat{Z}_i^U . In the predictive search
 13 procedure, we define an incumbent index set PS , which is the set of indices for variable Z_i^U . The
 14 superincumbent index set PS^{SS} is the incumbent index set in the previous iteration. At the begin of
 15 each iteration, u indices from $\{Z_1^U, Z_2^U, \dots, Z_n^U\} \setminus PS$ are selected, and the following steps are taken
 16 to update PS^{SS} and PS : $PS^{SS} := PS$; add u indices into PS . The entire feasible region of Z_i^U ,
 17 indicated by Φ , is thus partitioned into the incumbent region: $\Phi^P = \{Z \in \Phi \mid Z_i^U = \hat{Z}_i^U, Z_i^U \in PS\}$,
 18 the superincumbent region: $\Phi^{SS} = \{Z \in \{\Phi \setminus \Phi^P\} \mid Z_i^U = \hat{Z}_i^U, Z_i^U \in PS^{SS}\}$, and the nonincumbent
 19 region Φ^N , which is the remaining region.

20 To summarize above, the pseudocode of the PS-ALNS algorithm is shown in Algorithm 1.
 21 At the beginning of PS-ALNS, a feasible solution can be set by letting all $Z_i^U = 0$, meaning
 22 that all nodes are truck nodes, and use ALNS to solve the corresponding subproblem. In each
 23 iteration, firstly, u indices are selected using the index selection process, and form the PS, PS^{SS} .
 24 Secondly, the value sampling process is performed to sample values of Z_i^U in the incumbent region,
 25 superincumbent region, and nonincumbent region, respectively. Thereafter, each group of sampled
 26 values leads to a routing subproblem with predetermined drone nodes and truck nodes. This
 27 subproblem is solved by the ALNS algorithm. Lastly, PS and PS^{SS} are updated based on the
 28 results from the subproblem. Details within these steps are further described in section 4.2.3.

Algorithm 1 PS-ALNS Framework

Let $Z = [0, 0, \dots, 0]$, solve this subproblem using ALNS.

$PS, PS^{SS} = \emptyset$

while Stop Criteria Not Met **do**

Index Selection: u indices are selected and added into PS , and PS^{SS} is PS without u recently added indices.

Value Sampling: From the incumbent region, superincumbent region, and nonincumbent region, sample the values of undetermined Z_i^U and forms N incumbent subproblems, N superincumbent subproblems, and N nonincumbent subproblems.

Evaluation: For each subproblem, the ALNS algorithm is used to solve this problem and find the corresponding solution value.

Update: Based on the solution value of each subproblem, update PS and \hat{Z}_i^U .

end while

4.2. Predictive Search

In the predictive search process within the PS-ALNS algorithm, a prediction method is adopted to obtain the probability $\pi(Z_i^U)$, which is the probability of $Z_i^U = 1$. This probability is leveraged in index selection and value sampling explained as follows.

To get the probability, the logistic regression algorithm is used. For each node, the output parameter is 1 if this node is served by a drone, otherwise 0. The input features of a node include:

- weight of demand required by this customer;
- distance to three nearest neighbor node;
- demand weight of three nearest neighbor node;
- solution value in the relaxed model.

4.2.1. Index Selection

In each iteration, u indices are selected into the incumbent set. Here we select the item without replication using the round robin algorithm with the weight function in (21). This proposed weight

1 function guarantees that if the best-known value of a variable is closer to the predicted value, it is
2 more likely to be chosen.

$$W_i = \frac{1 - |\hat{Z}_i^U - \pi(Z_i^U)|}{\sum_{i \in C \setminus PS}} \quad (21)$$

3 4.2.2. Value Sampling

4 To formulate the subproblem in the incumbent region, the values of variables in PS are fixed
5 to be the best solution found. In terms of the remaining binary variables, they take value 1 with
6 probability $\pi(Z_i^U)$. To formulate the subproblem in the superincumbent region, all variables in
7 the PS^{SS} are fixed to be the best-known value, and the remaining binary variables take value
8 1 with probability $\pi(Z_i^U)$. The sampled values for this superincumbent subproblem may be in
9 the incumbent set, in that case, it will be sampled again. To formulate the subproblem in the
10 non-incumbent region, all variables take value 1 with probability $\pi(Z_i^U)$. If these sampled values
11 are in the incumbent set or superincumbent set, they will be sampled again as well.

12 4.2.3. Updating Step

13 The update steps in each iteration round are different based on which region the optimal solution
14 comes from, and they are listed below.

- 15 • If the optimal solution is selected in the incumbent region, the size of the incumbent set needs
16 to be considered. If the size is not larger than the customized upper bound, the incumbent set
17 in the next iteration will be the incumbent set in this round. Otherwise, the incumbent set in
18 the next round is the superincumbent set in this round.
- 19 • If the optimal solution is selected in the superincumbent region, the incumbent set in the next
20 round is the superincumbent set in this round.
- 21 • If the optimal solution is selected in the nonincumbent region, the incumbent set in the next
22 round is an empty set, which means the predictive search procedure will be restarted.

1 4.3. ALNS

2 The adaptive large neighbourhood search algorithm shown in Algorithm 2 is adopted to solve the
3 subproblem with truck nodes and drone nodes fixed. The ALNS involves an adaptive selection of
4 the removal and repair operators, the main objective of which is to search unexplored yet promising
5 solution region through large neighborhood updates.

6 **Algorithm 2** ALNS

7 Construct an initial solution S with Regret Insert
8 $C_{cni}^{ALNS} \leftarrow 0, S_{best} \leftarrow S$
9 **while** not exceeding time limit **do**
10 $\alpha \leftarrow \min\{\alpha_{max}, \alpha_{min} + \alpha_{rate} \times C_{cni}^{ALNS}\} \times n$
11 Select removal operator to remove α customers from the S
12 Select repair operator to repair S
13 $\epsilon_{TS} \leftarrow \min\{C_{cni}^{ALNS} + \phi_{cni}, 2\phi_{cni}\}$
14 $S \leftarrow TS(S, \epsilon_{TS})$
15 **if** $f(S) < f(S_{best})$ **then**
16 $C_{cni}^{ALNS} \leftarrow 0, S_{best} \leftarrow S$
17 **else**
18 $C_{cni}^{ALNS} \leftarrow C_{cni}^{ALNS} + 1$
19 **end if**
20 Update scores and probability for removal and repair operators
21 **end while**
22 **return** S_{best}

23 4.3.1. Initial Solution

24 A greedy insertion-based strategy is employed to create the initial solution. First, all the truck
25 nodes are inserted into the truck routes one after another. After the insert operation is done, all the
26 possible positions are checked, and the positions which lead to the minimal objective value will be
27 chosen. Second, if there is a drone node l with remaining demand, all possible pairs of (i, j) , such
28 that i, l, j forms a valid drone flight, are chosen. The pair with the highest drone capacity w_{ijl} will

1 be selected, and the remaining demand of drone node l is reduced by w_{ijl} . The insertion of drone
 2 assignment stops when the demands of all drone nodes are satisfied or no more feasible (i, j) pairs
 3 can be found for the remaining drone nodes.

4 4.3.2. Removal Operators

5 In the VRPD-S problem, there are two types of scheduling: truck route scheduling and drone
 6 nodes' demand to schedule. Therefore, in the ALNS, the removal that perturbs both truck routes
 7 and drone node demand assignment needs to be considered as the update mechanism.

8 The number of truck nodes and drone node demand assignment to be removed is controlled
 9 by the parameter α . When some truck node removal operators are selected, the number of truck
 10 nodes to be removed is αn . When some drone route removal operators are selected, the total served
 11 demand of drone nodes to be removed is $\alpha \sum_{i \in C; z_i^u = 1} w_i$. The removal of a truck node could affect
 12 the corresponding drone route. Suppose there is a drone visit $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$, and the truck node
 13 between node i and j is removed, the truck's arrival time at node j will be reduced, which leads
 14 to the reduction of a drone hovering time. Thus, every time such a node is removed, the satisfied
 15 demand on drone node l will also be updated. When the truck node i or node j is removed, the
 16 drone visit $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$ will also be removed, and the satisfied demand on drone node l will be
 17 updated. The details of removal operators are specified as follows.

18 **The worst removal of truck node** Remove the truck nodes such that the reduction of time
 19 makespan is the largest. Formally, the reduction of time makespan for solution S and truck node i
 20 is defined as $\Delta C = f(S) - f(\bar{S})$, where \bar{S} is the solution by removing the truck node i . The truck
 21 nodes are removed one by one until the total number of removed truck nodes is larger than αn .

22 **Random removal of truck node** The truck nodes are removed randomly one by one such that
 23 the total number of removed truck nodes is larger than αn .

24 **Worse removal of drone route** Select the route that has the largest makespan, and remove one
 25 drone node from it.

26 **Random removal of drone route** Select a drone route $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$ randomly, and remove it
 27 from the solution.

1 4.3.3. Repair Operators

2 The repair operators are designed to insert the unvisited truck nodes into the current solution
3 and assign unfulfilled drone node demands to some drone routes. In the repair steps, the truck
4 nodes are repaired first, and after that, all unfulfilled drone node demands are repaired. This repair
5 operation is sequentially applied until all truck nodes are visited and all drone node demands are
6 satisfied. Due to possible infeasible solutions, some truck nodes or drone node demands cannot be
7 repaired. These nodes and demands pose a penalty to the objective function value.

8 The insertion of truck nodes will affect some drone visits. For example, if there is a drone route
9 $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$ and a new truck node is inserted between node i and node j , the truck's arrival time at
10 j will be late. Thus, the drone may hover for a longer time and the capacity of this route will be
11 reduced. As a result, each time such a truck node is inserted, we will update the capacity of the
12 affected drone route.

13 **Truck node insertion with least additional time** The truck nodes are inserted in a random
14 order one after another into a route such that the additional time is minimized.

15 **Truck node insertion with least additional time with Perturbation** The truck nodes are
16 inserted in a random order one after another. When choosing a route to insert, the additional time is
17 perturbed by a random factor $d \in [0.8, 1.2]$. The route with the smallest perturbed additional time
18 is chosen.

19 **Regret insertion of drone route** For the drone node l with unsatisfied demand and a pair of
20 feasible truck nodes i, j , the insertion of drone route $i \rightarrow l \rightarrow j$ will lead to some additional time.
21 The regret insertion value is defined as the difference between the additional time when the optimal
22 pair of truck nodes are chosen and when the second optimal pair of truck nodes are chosen. As long
23 as there are several drone nodes with unsatisfied demand, the drone node with the highest regret
24 insertion value is chosen and the corresponding drone route is inserted into the solution. When
25 there are multiple drones with the same optimal regret insertion value, the drone route with the
26 capacity closest to the unsatisfied demand is chosen.

5. Computational Experiments

In this section, we present the results of a series of experiments to examine the effectiveness of the VRPD-S model and the performance of the proposed algorithm PS-ALNS. Code was implemented in Python3.10 and run on a Ubuntu 18.04.3 LTS server with Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4216 CPU at 2.10 GHz. We use solver CPLEX 12.8.0 to solve the MILP model.

We first describe the newly generated test instances for the VRPD-S in section 5.1. The detailed experimental is provided following. Section 5.2 shows results of the logistic regression part. Lastly, we apply the algorithm to solve test instances with small, medium and large scales respectively in section 5.3, 5.4 and 5.5.

5.1. Test Instances

The test we used is constructed from SDVRPLIB data proposed in Belenguer et al. (2000). When a data instance with size n is generated, we first randomly select an instance from SDVRPLIB data with a size larger than n , then n nodes are selected randomly to generate such a small data instance. In this work, we generated 3 different data sets with 10, 20, and 100 customers (labeled as T-10, T-20, and T-100). Since the probability is needed in the predictive search part, we also generated a set of 500 instances with 7-15 customers for training purposes. This data set is labeled as Train-500. The speed of the truck is fixed to be 1 and the speed of the drone is fixed to be 2. In terms of the drone profile, we set $Q = 80$, $\theta = 800$, $\alpha = 1$, $w^U = 5$.

5.2. Training Data and Logistic Regression

The Train-500 data set is divided into a training set with 400 data instances and a validation set with 100 data instances. The logistic regression model is built based on the training set. A performance evaluation test is conducted on the validation set. Accuracy of this logistic regression classifier on validation set: 0.86. This model forms a receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC) with AUC equals to 0.69, as shown in Fig. 2.

5.3. Performance on Small Scale Instances

For each instance in data set T-10, we use both CPLEX and PS-ALNS to solve this problem with $k = 2$, i.e. there are two vehicles in use. The result is reported in Table 3, where column Δ

Figure 2: ROC and lift curve

- 1 measures the difference between the best feasible solution found by CPLEX and PS-ALNS method.
- 2 Formally, for a instance, LB and UB denotes the lower bound and upper bound from CPLEX, c_{best}
- 3 is the optimal solution from PS-ALNS, and the value in column Δ is $\frac{c_{best}-UB}{UB} \times 100\%$.
- 4 The result shows that CPLEX can solve all the small-scale instances, and PS-ALNS can solve
- 5 most of these instances optimally, and for the remaining cases, Δ is always smaller than 5%. In
- 6 terms of CPU time to get the solution, Cplex is significantly greater than PS-ALNS.

Table 3: Results of numerical experiments for T-10 from two algorithms

S/N	Cplex			PS-ALNS		Δ
	LB	UB	CPU time	c_{best}	CPU time	
T-10-1	126.21	126.21	15.22/s	126.21	3.1/s	0%
T-10-2	107.99	107.99	88.44/s	107.99	4.2/s	0%
T-10-3	150.94	150.94	74.01/s	150.94	2.7/s	0%
T-10-4	84.76	84.76	122.61/s	86.92	7.8/s	4.9%
T-10-5	196.61	196.61	48.02/s	196.61	13.6/s	0%
T-10-6	92.60	92.60	16.44/s	92.60	7.9/s	0%
T-10-7	129.06	129.06	24.351/s	129.06	2.4/s	0%
T-10-8	131.29	131.29	23.970/s	131.39	2.3/s	0%
T-10-9	55.73	55.73	41.504/s	57.62	1.1/s	3.4%
T-10-10	65.65	65.65	111.46/s	65.65	1.7/s	0%

1

2 *5.4. Performance on Medium Scale Instances*

3 For each instance in data set T-20, we use both CPLEX and PS-ALNS to solve this problem
 4 with $k = 2$, i.e. there are two vehicles in use. Since the size of each instance is larger than T-10, it
 5 takes more time for CPLEX to find a solution. We set the time limit to be 1 hour (3,600s), and the
 6 CPLEX program will be terminated after the time limit is exceeded. The results are shown in Table
 7 **??**.

8 As shown in this table, CPLEX cannot solve the instance with 20 nodes within 3,600s, and the
 9 average gap is 60.66%. PS-ALNS can solve such instances within 30s, and provide a better result
 10 is better than *CPLEX*, and the average Δ is 29.49%.

Table 4: Results of numerical experiments for T-20 from two algorithms

S/N	Cplex				PS-ALNS		
	LB	UB	CPU time	gap	C_{best}	CPU time	Δ
T-20-1	270.52	93.95	3600/s	65.27%	167.65	28.8/s	-38.02%
T-20-2	339.37	124.88	3600/s	63.20%	269.54	15.5/s	-20.57%
T-20-3	464.44	166.20	3600/s	64.21%	254.56	26.9/s	-45.19%
T-20-4	169.45	83.23	3600/s	50.87%	96.58	9.2/s	-43.05%
T-20-5	211.96	81.59	3600/s	61.50%	158.86	3.8/s	-25.05%
T-20-6	166.30	73.23	3600/s	55.96%	101.75	15.7/s	-38.81%
T-20-7	179.33	77.51	3600/s	56.77%	120.27	5.6/s	-32.93%
T-20-8	239.30	86.49	3600/s	63.85%	228.90	3.4/s	-4.34%
T-20-9	151.96	73.23	3600/s	51.80%	121.04	13.0/s	-20.35%
T-20-10	193.42	51.84	3600/s	73.19%	141.90	25.1/s	-26.66%

11

12 *5.5. Performance on Large Scale Instances*

13 In terms of T-100, CPLEX cannot find a feasible solution. However, PS-ALNS is capable of
 14 finding feasible solution. We solve each instance in T-100 with $k = 2, 3, 5$, meaning there are 2, 3, 5
 15 vehicles available in this problem. The result is shown in table **??**. It indicates that with more
 16 vehicles in use, the total cost will be reduced. This result can be used as a benchmark reference for
 17 future studies. To better evaluate our algorithm, we set the time limit to be 30 minutes.

Table 5: Results of numerical experiments for T-30

S/N	k=2		k=3		k=5	
	C_{best}	CPU time	C_{best}	CPU time	C_{best}	CPU time
T-100-1	591.28	1800/s	386.17	1800/s	247.69	1800/s
T-100-2	785.18	1800/s	521.84	1800/s	362.40	1800/s
T-100-3	1248.04	1800/s	857.97	1800/s	534.95	1800/s
T-100-4	1098.64	1800/s	691.65	1800/s	481.71	1800/s
T-100-5	537.44	1800/s	365.39	1800/s	211.66	1800/s
T-100-6	441.56	1800/s	295.50	1800/s	211.68	1800/s
T-100-7	408.34	1800/s	258.39	1800/s	197.49	1800/s
T-100-8	330.97	1800/s	209.86	1800/s	162.56	1800/s
T-100-9	729.63	1800/s	457.06	1800/s	288.68	1800/s
T-10-10	775.73	1800/s	513.84	1800/s	341.09	1800/s

1

2 6. Conclusions

3 This paper introduces a new variant of the VRPD, which extends the classic truck-drone delivery
4 problem by considering the interconnections of drone physical limitations reflected by the endurance
5 constraints, and split delivery strategy. Unlike prior studies, we treat customer demands as splittable
6 to be served by drones. A MILP formulation is first built to model the problem, which is solvable by
7 CPLEX. To tackle VRPD-S instances more efficiently, we next construct a heuristic approach. The
8 proposed PS-ALNS algorithm is based on the predictive search for the truck visiting node decision,
9 and local search for the drone split delivery scheduling and synchronization with truck visiting
10 nodes. To assess the effectiveness of the two-step heuristic method and investigate the effects of
11 important variables and parameters, extensive numerical experiments based on two different types
12 of benchmark examples are carried out. The efficiency of last-mile delivery can be improved with
13 the suggested drone split delivery approach. These findings serve as a powerful impetus for both
14 additional academic study and efforts to make this application commercially viable for the logistics
15 sector. Future research potentials are the extension of optimization model formulation to include
16 additional features such as heterogeneous fleet, time windows, pickup and delivery services, and
17 the combination of split delivery with multi-visits per drone flight.

1 **References**

- 2 Agatz, N., Bouman, P., & Schmidt, M. (2018). Optimization approaches for the traveling salesman problem with drone.
3 *Transportation Science*, 52, 965–981.
- 4 Aleman, R. E., Zhang, X., & Hill, R. R. (2010). An adaptive memory algorithm for the split delivery vehicle routing
5 problem. *Journal of Heuristics*, 16, 441–473.
- 6 Archetti, C., Bianchessi, N., & Speranza, M. G. (2011a). A column generation approach for the split delivery vehicle
7 routing problem. *Networks*, 58, 241–254.
- 8 Archetti, C., Feillet, D., Gendreau, M., & Speranza, M. G. (2011b). Complexity of the vrp and sdvrp. *Transportation
9 Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 19, 741–750.
- 10 Archetti, C., & Speranza, M. G. (2008). The split delivery vehicle routing problem: A survey. In *The vehicle routing
11 problem: Latest advances and new challenges* (pp. 103–122). Springer.
- 12 Archetti, C., & Speranza, M. G. (2012). Vehicle routing problems with split deliveries. *International transactions in
13 operational research*, 19, 3–22.
- 14 Archetti, C., & Speranza, M. G. (2014). A survey on matheuristics for routing problems. *EURO Journal on
15 Computational Optimization*, 2, 223–246.
- 16 Belenguer, J.-M., Martinez, M., & Mota, E. (2000). A lower bound for the split delivery vehicle routing problem.
17 *Operations research*, 48, 801–810.
- 18 Boudia, M., Louly, M. A. O., & Prins, C. (2006). A memetic algorithm with population management for a production-
19 distribution problem. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 39, 541–546.
- 20 Bouman, P., Agatz, N., & Schmidt, M. (2018). Dynamic programming approaches for the traveling salesman problem
21 with drone. *Networks*, 72, 528–542.
- 22 Campos, V., Glover, F., Laguna, M., & Martí, R. (2001). An experimental evaluation of a scatter search for the linear
23 ordering problem. *Journal of Global Optimization*, 21, 397–414.
- 24 Cavani, S., Iori, M., & Roberti, R. (2021). Exact methods for the traveling salesman problem with multiple drones.
25 *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 130, 103280.
- 26 Chen, S., Golden, B., & Wasil, E. (2007). The split delivery vehicle routing problem: Applications, algorithms, test
27 problems, and computational results. *Networks: An International Journal*, 49, 318–329.
- 28 Choi, Y., & Schonfeld, P. M. (2017). Optimization of multi-package drone deliveries considering battery capacity. In
29 *Proceedings of the 96th Annual Meeting of the Transportation Research Board, Washington, DC, USA* (pp. 8–12).
- 30 Derigs, U., Li, B., & Vogel, U. (2010). Local search-based metaheuristics for the split delivery vehicle routing problem.
31 *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 61, 1356–1364.
- 32 Gulczynski, D., Golden, B., & Wasil, E. (2010). The split delivery vehicle routing problem with minimum delivery
33 amounts. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 46, 612–626.

- 1 Ha, Q. M., Deville, Y., Pham, Q. D., & Ha, M. H. (2018). On the min-cost traveling salesman problem with drone.
2 *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 86, 597–621.
- 3 Ha, Q. M., Deville, Y., Pham, Q. D., & Hà, M. H. (2020). A hybrid genetic algorithm for the traveling salesman
4 problem with drone. *Journal of Heuristics*, 26, 219–247.
- 5 Irnich, S., Schneider, M., & Vigo, D. (2014). Chapter 9: Four variants of the vehicle routing problem. In *Vehicle*
6 *Routing: Problems, Methods, and Applications, Second Edition* (pp. 241–271). SIAM.
- 7 Liu, W., Zhou, Y., Liu, W., Qiu, J., Xie, N., Chang, X., & Chen, J. (2021). A hybrid acs-vtm algorithm for the vehicle
8 routing problem with simultaneous delivery & pickup and real-time traffic condition. *Computers & Industrial*
9 *Engineering*, 162, 107747.
- 10 Liu, Y., Liu, Z., Shi, J., Wu, G., & Pedrycz, W. (2020). Two-echelon routing problem for parcel delivery by cooperated
11 truck and drone. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, .
- 12 Luo, Z., Poon, M., Zhang, Z., Liu, Z., & Lim, A. (2021). The multi-visit traveling salesman problem with multi-drones.
13 *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 128, 103172.
- 14 Macrina, G., Pugliese, L. D. P., Guerriero, F., & Laporte, G. (2020). Drone-aided routing: A literature review.
15 *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 120, 102762.
- 16 Marques, G., Sadykov, R., Deschamps, J.-C., & Dupas, R. (2020). An improved branch-cut-and-price algorithm for the
17 two-echelon capacitated vehicle routing problem. *Computers & Operations Research*, 114, 104833.
- 18 Moreno, L., De AragãO, M. P., & Uchoa, E. (2010). Improved lower bounds for the split delivery vehicle routing
19 problem. *Operations Research Letters*, 38, 302–306.
- 20 Murray, C. C., & Chu, A. G. (2015). The flying sidekick traveling salesman problem: Optimization of drone-assisted
21 parcel delivery. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 54, 86–109.
- 22 Ozsoydan, F. B., & Sipahioglu, A. (2013). Heuristic solution approaches for the cumulative capacitated vehicle routing
23 problem. *Optimization*, 62, 1321–1340.
- 24 Paul, A., Kumar, R. S., Rout, C., & Goswami, A. (2021). Designing a multi-depot multi-period vehicle routing problem
25 with time window: hybridization of tabu search and variable neighbourhood search algorithm. *Sādhanā*, 46, 1–11.
- 26 Poikonen, S., Golden, B., & Wasil, E. A. (2019). A branch-and-bound approach to the traveling salesman problem with
27 a drone. *INFORMS Journal on Computing*, 31, 335–346.
- 28 Poikonen, S., Wang, X., & Golden, B. (2017). The vehicle routing problem with drones: Extended models and
29 connections. *Networks*, 70, 34–43.
- 30 Roberti, R., & Ruthmair, M. (2021). Exact methods for the traveling salesman problem with drone. *Transportation*
31 *Science*, 55, 315–335.
- 32 Schermer, D., Moeini, M., & Wendt, O. (2018). Algorithms for solving the vehicle routing problem with drones. In
33 *Asian Conference on Intelligent Information and Database Systems* (pp. 352–361). Springer.
- 34 Silva, M. M., Subramanian, A., & Ochi, L. S. (2015). An iterated local search heuristic for the split delivery vehicle

1 routing problem. *Computers & Operations Research*, 53, 234–249.

2 Toth, P., & Vigo, D. (2002). Models, relaxations and exact approaches for the capacitated vehicle routing problem.

3 *Discrete Applied Mathematics*, 123, 487–512.

4 Tuzun, D., & Burke, L. I. (1999). A two-phase tabu search approach to the location routing problem. *European journal*

5 *of operational research*, 116, 87–99.

6 Vásquez, S. A., Angulo, G., & Klapp, M. A. (2021). An exact solution method for the tsp with drone based on

7 decomposition. *Computers & Operations Research*, 127, 105127.

8 Wang, X., Poikonen, S., & Golden, B. (2017). The vehicle routing problem with drones: Several worst-case results.

9 *Optimization Letters*, 11, 679–697.

10 Wilck IV, J. H., & Cavalier, T. M. (2012). A genetic algorithm for the split delivery vehicle routing problem, .

11 Wu, T. (2022). Predictive search for capacitated multi-item lot sizing problems. *INFORMS Journal on Computing*, 34,

12 385–406.

13 Yurek, E. E., & Ozmutlu, H. C. (2018). A decomposition-based iterative optimization algorithm for traveling salesman

14 problem with drone. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 91, 249–262.

15 Zhang, J., Campbell, J. F., II, D. C. S., & Hupman, A. C. (2020). Energy consumption models for delivery drones: A

16 comparison and assessment. Available online.

17 Zhang, J., Campbell, J. F., Sweeney II, D. C., & Hupman, A. C. (2021). Energy consumption models for delivery

18 drones: A comparison and assessment. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 90, 102668.

19 Zhou, H., Qin, H., Cheng, C., & Rousseau, L.-M. (). A branch-and-price algorithm for the vehicle routing problem

20 with drones, .